

Antibacterial Efficacy of *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical Almond) Leaf Extracts on Some Selected Clinical Pathogens

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Abstract

The antibacterial efficacy of *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical almond) leaf crude extracts was carried out using agar “well” diffusion method on some clinical pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) which were obtained from Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State. The ethanol and aqueous extracts were obtained using ethanol and warm water, as solvents for the extraction respectively. The antibacterial efficacy testing of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts indicates appreciable activity against the pathogens with the varying concentrations (10, 30, 50 and 70 mg/ml) used. The phytochemical studies were carried on the ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf, in order to ascertain the presence of certain bioactive compounds. The screening revealed the presence of some important bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides and glycosides which could be responsible for the observed efficacy. The varying concentrations of the extracts were introduced to prepared “well” inside the plates, the plates were then incubated at 37^oC for 24 hours, the zone of inhibition were then measured after the incubation period. The highest activity of 24.0mm was recorded for the ethanol extract on *Salmonella typhi* at the highest concentration of 70mg/ml used while the aqueous extract indicates the highest activity of 20.0mm against the two test bacteria at the highest concentration of 70mg/ml used. Ciprofloxacin antibiotic impregnated disc was used for the positive control. The minimum inhibitory concentration and minimum bactericidal concentration study of both the ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf on the test bacteria indicates that the extracts has both bacteriostatic and bactericidal efficacy. The responses of the test bacteria to the crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf and the presence of very important bioactive compounds in the plant leaf has provided clue of using the leaf of *Terminalia catappa* for medicinal remedy against disease caused by the test bacteria under study. Toxicity level of this plant leaf should be determined for safety purpose.

Keywords: Agar well, Antibacterial, Efficacy, Leaf extracts, Pathogens, *Terminalia catappa*,

1.0 Introduction

Terminalia catappa L. commonly known as Tropical almond is a *Combretaceous* plant whose leaves are widely used as a folk medicine in Southeast Asia for the treatment of dermatosis and hepatitis [5]. This species is globally distributed from Indo-Maleisa to Australia. Tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa*) is a large, spreading tree now distributed throughout the tropics in coastal environments [11]. The tree is tolerant of strong

winds, salt spray, and moderately high salinity in the root zone. It grows principally in freely drained, well aerated; sandy soils [5].

The species has traditionally been very important for coastal communities, providing a wide range of non-wood products and services. It has a spreading, fibrous root system and plays a vital role in coastline stabilization [11]. It is widely planted throughout the tropics, especially along sandy seashores, for shade, ornamental purposes,

and edible nuts. The timber makes a useful and decorative general-purpose hardwood and is well suited for conversion into furniture and interior building timbers [11].

Fruits are produced from about 3 years of age, and the nutritious, tasty seed kernels may be eaten immediately after extraction. Its preferred scientific name is *Terminalia catappa* L. Family is Combretaceae (combretum family). Non-preferred scientific names are *Phytolacca javanica*, *Terminalia mauritiana* Blanco *Terminalia moluccana* Lamk. *Terminalia procera* Roxb. Common names are *alite* (Solomon Islands pidgin) 'autaraa, 'aua, 'auarii, 'auari'iroa (Societies) *kamanihaole*, *kamani 'ula*, false *kamani* (Hawaii) *kauariki*, *kaukauariki*, *taraire* (Cook's: Mangaia) *natapoa* (Vanuatu: Bislama) tropical, beach, or Indian almond (English) *talie* (Samoa) *talise* (Papua New Guinea: TokPisin) *tavola*, *tivi* (Fiji) *telie* (Tonga, 'Uvea, Futuna, Tokelau, Tuvalu). The fruit is high in tannic acid and this could stain cars, pavement and sidewalks. It also causes significant litter on the ground [10].

There has been renewed interest in the emulsion as a vehicle for delivering drugs to the body as it has been found to have several advantageous characteristics, frequently enhancing the bioavailability of the drug substance [6]. In an emulsion the therapeutic properties and spreading ability of the constituents are increased. Water-in-oil emulsions are employed more widely for the treatment of dry skin and emollient applications [6].

The issue of resistance of bacterial infection to some drugs and other skin remedy available in the market has sparked up the interest in the search for alternative sources of antimicrobial agents; especially natural sources like plants and plant products which could be active against major causative agents [4]. Drug resistant strains cause severe problems in many infections including wounds, burns, gastrointestinal infections and other disorders of microbial origin. One of the ways to prevent antibiotic resistance is by using new compounds that are not based on existing

synthetic antimicrobial agents [9]. Plants contain a wide range of bioactive compounds which makes them potential source of antimicrobial agents [4]. *Terminalia catappa* leaves have been reported to have antimicrobial and antiparasitic potentials and maybe due to the presence of some important bioactive compound, which could be of ethno-medicinal values [15]. This is why; this study is with the view to determine the bioactivity of *Terminalia catappa* leaf extracts against some selected clinical pathogens to provide clue for the possibility of using this plant leave for alternative source of antibiotic against the bacteria under study. The aim of this research work is to determine the antibacterial efficacy of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts against some clinical pathogens, such as (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*). Through the following objectives;

- To determine the phytochemical constituents of crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical almond) leaf.
- To determine the antibacterial efficacy of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts against the clinical pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*)
- To determine the MIC and MBC of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts against the clinical pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*)

1.1 Botanical clarification

Kingdom: Plantae (Plants)

Subkingdom: *Tracheobionta* (Vascular plants)

Super division: Spermatophyta (Seed plants)

Division: *Magnoliophyta* (Flowering plants)

Subdivision: *Spermatophytina* (spermatophytes, seed plants, phanérogames)

Class: *Magnoliopsida* (*Dicotyledons*)

Subclass: *Rosidae*

Order: *Myrtales*

Family: *Combretaceae*

Genus: *Terminalia* L. (tropical almond)

Species: *Terminalia catappa* L. [8].

Tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa*) [12].

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample Collection

The *Terminalia catappa* leaves were collected in Fadama area of old town along Maikera road in Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State, Nigeria. The samples were then transported to Microbiology laboratory, Department of Science Technology, Waziri Umaru Federal Polytechnic Birnin Kebbi. The plant samples were authenticated by a botanist in the department and were processed (Batch-CNE024).

2.1.1 Sample Processing

The collected *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical almond) leaves were washed to remove dust and allowed to dry under shade for a period of 7 days. The leaves were then pound using mortar and pestle to obtain a fine powder of the sample and was stored in a plastic bag and kept until when needed [7].

2.1.2 Extraction of Plant material

About 200g of powdered sample of the *Terminalia catappa* leaves was weighed and soak in 1000ml of ethanol and was then allowed to stay for three (3) days, after which, the solution was sieved and the extract was placed on a water bath and concentrated in water bath at 40°C for evaporation to take place. The ethanol extract was then collected and stored for further used. This same technique was applied for the aqueous extract using warm water [7].

2.2 Media Preparation

All the media used in this research work were prepared in accordance to the manufacturer's

instructions as contain in the label on the media containers [16].

2.3 Confirmation of bacteria

The test organisms (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) used in this research work, were clinical pathogens collected from Microbiology Laboratory of Federal Medical Centre, Birnin Kebbi. The pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) were then transported to Microbiology Laboratory of Department of Science Technology and were confirmed by sub-culturing, Gram staining and then subjected to specific biochemical confirmatory test and maintained on nutrient agar medium. They were then kept as stock cultures in the refrigerator until when need [3].

2.4 Phytochemical Screening

2.4.1 Tests for Tannins

Exactly 0.2 g of extracts was stirred with distilled water and filtered. Ferric chloride was added to the filtrate. A blue-black, green or blue-green precipitate was taken as an evidence for the presence of tannins [13]

2.4.2 Test for Flavonoids

A little amount of magnesium powder and few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to 3 ml of the extracts. A red or intense red colouration indicates the presence of flavonoides [14].

2.4.3 Test for Glycosides

The extracts was hydrolyzed with HCl solution and neutralized with NaOH solution. A few drops of Fehlings solution A and B was added. Red precipitate indicates the presence of glycosides [14].

2.4.4 Test for Cardiac Glycoside (Keller-Killani Test)

Exactly 0.2 g of the extracts was dissolved in 2 ml of glacial acetic acid containing one drop of ferric chloride solution followed by the addition of 1 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. A brown ring at the interface confirmed the presence of cardiac glycoside [14].

2.4.5 Tests for Alkaloids

Exactly 0.2 g of extracts was shaken with 1 % HCl for two minutes. The mixture was filtered and drops of Dragendorff's reagent added. Formation of a precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids [14].

2.5 Antibacterial Testing

2.5.1 Formulation of varying concentration of the extracts

About 1g of the ethanol extract was weighed and placed in 10ml of distilled water and the same was done for 3g, 5g and 7g in other to obtained varying concentrations of 10mg/ml, 30mg/ml, 50mg/ml, and 70mg/ml respectively. The same procedure was repeated for the aqueous extract [7].

2.5.2 Preparation of inoculums

Agar "well" diffusion method was used to determine the antimicrobial efficacy of the crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf on the test pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*). The selected strains of the pathogens were inoculated into 5mls of sterile nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. "Wells" were made on the prepared Mueller Hinton agar. The organisms from the broth culture were then strike separately on the plates containing the Mueller Hinton agar and the varying concentrations of 10mg/ml, 30mg/ml, 50mg/ml, and 70mg/ml of the crude extracts were then placed on the plate

containing the organisms. This was done in duplicate and the plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The diameter of the zone inhibition were measured, recorded and expressed in millimeters. Ciprofloxacin impregnated antibiotic disc was used as control [7].

2.6 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration was determined by the tube dilution methods. Each concentration of the extracts was dispensed into sterile nutrient broth. Each test tube was inoculated with 1.0ml of the test organisms. This was done in duplicate and was incubated at 37°C for 24hours. The tubes were examined for bacterial growth by observing turbidity. The lowest concentration where there was no turbidity was observed and record for MIC [2].

For each set of test tubes in MIC determine, a loopful of broth were collected from those tubes that shows no turbidity and was inoculate on sterile nutrient agar plates by streaking and were incubated at 37°C for 24hours, this was done in duplicate. The concentration, at which no visible growth was observed, was record as MBC [2].

3.0 Results and Discussions

Table 1: Shows the results of the phytochemical Compounds present in *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts

Phytochemical Compounds	Level of Presence	
	Ethanol Extract	Aqueous Extract
Tannins	++	+++
Glycosides	+	+
Flavonoids	++	++
Alkaloids	+	++
Cardiae glycoside	++	+++

Key: ++ = Slightly Present, + = Moderately Present, - = Absent

The phytochemical studies of the ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf, revealed the presence of some important phytochemical constituents such as alkaloids, tannins, flavoroids, cardiac glycosides and glycosides as seen in Table 3.

Table 2: Shows Results of the main zone of inhibition of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts obtained against some clinical pathogens

Extract / Test Bacteria	Concentration in (mg/ml)/ Zone of inhibition in (mm)				
	10	30	50	70	Control
Ethanol Extract					
<i>S aureus</i>	14.0	14.0	18.0	20.0	20.0
<i>S typhi</i>	12.0	18.0	18.0	24.0	26.0
Aqueous Extract					
<i>S aureus</i>	10.0	16.0	18.0	20.0	20.0
<i>S typhi</i>	14.0	14.0	14.0	20.0	26.0

Key: mg/ml = Milligram/ml, mm = Millimeter, Control = Ciprofloxacin

The antibacterial efficacy of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts was carried out using agar well diffusion method on some clinical pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) which were obtained from Federal Medical Centre Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State. The ethanol and aqueous extracts were obtained using ethanol and warm water, as solvents for the extraction.

The antibacterial efficacy testing of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts shows varying degree of activities on the pathogens (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) at the different concentrations (10, 30, 50 and 70 mg/ml), as seen in Table2, the ethanol extracts shows activities of 14.0, 14.0, 18.0 and 20.0 mm on *Staphylococcus*

aureus and 12.0, 18.0, 18.0 and 24.0 mm against *Salmonella typhi* with the different concentrations. The highest activity of 24.0mm of the ethanol extract was recorded on *Salmonella typhi* at the highest concentration 70mg/ml used while the aqueous extract shows activity of 10.0, 16.0, 18.0 and 20.0 mm on *Staphylococcus aureus* and 14.0, 14.0, 14.0 and 20.0mm on *Salmonella typhi* at the same concentrations used. The highest activity of 20.0mm of the aqueous extract was recorded on the two test bacteria at the highest concentration of 70mg/ml. Ciprofloxacin antibiotic impregnated disc was used for the positive control which shows activity of 20.0mm on *Staphylococcus aureus* and 26.0mm on *Salmonella typhi*.

Table 3: Shows the minimum inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum bacteriacidal Concentration (MBC) results of *Terminalia catappa* leaf crude extracts obtained against some clinical pathogens

Extracts / Test Bacteria	MIC Values	MBC Values
Ethanol Extract		
<i>S. aureus</i>	1.09375	0.546875
<i>S typhi</i>	1.09375	0.546875
Aqueous Extract		
<i>S. aureus</i>	4.375	2.1875
<i>S typhi</i>	1.09375	0.546875

Key: mg/ml = Milligram/ml, mm = Millimeter

From Table 3, the MIC and MBC values are 1.09375 and 0.546875 on *Staphylococcus aureus* and 4.6875 and 2.34375 *Salmonella typhi* for the ethanol extracts while the values for the aqueous extracts are 1.09375 and 0.546875 on *Staphylococcus aureus* and 1.09375 and 0.546875 on *Salmonella typhi*. These results indicate that *Terminalia catappa* leaf has high inhibitory and cidal effects even at concentration of less than 1mg/ml.

4.0 Discussion

The result of this research clearly showed *Terminalia catappa* (Tropical almond) leaf crude extracts possess the presence of many important phytochemical compounds that can trigger antibacterial efficacy. The phytochemicals is as seen in table 1. This finding is in-line the work of [8] who reported that the aqueous extract from red fallen leaves contains tannins, six phenolic compounds such as p-hydroxybenzoic acid, 4-hydroxyphenylpropionic acid, m-coumaric acid,

3,4-dihydroxybenzoic acid, p-coumaric acid and gallic acid Almond is a popular nut rich in minerals, vitamins, proteins, fibres and other substances which promote a healthy life.

The antibacterial testing carried out indicates that the *Terminalia catappa* leaf ethanol and aqueous crude extracts shows appreciable efficacy against the test bacteria. The result shows that both the ethanol and aqueous extract are within the range of activity of the control used. The efficacy of the ethanol extract surpassed that the aqueous extract on *Salmonella typhi*. It was also observed that the efficacy of the extracts increases against the test bacteria with increasing concentrations of both extracts. These results agrees with the findings of [1] who reported that extracts of *Terminalia catappa* have high activities against both gram positive and gram negative bacteria. *Terminalia catappa* a leaf extracts was also reported to have antimicrobial and antiparasitic potentials and which may be due to the presence of some important bioactive compound, which could be of ethno-medicinal values [15].

The minimum inhibitory concentration and minimum bactericidal concentration study of both the ethanol and aqueous crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf against the test bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi* indicates that both extract has bacteriostatic and bactericidal potentials. Thus, the reason for the high antibacterial efficacy observed in this research. From the findings of this research work, it has been observed that *Terminalia catappa* leaf has shown tendency to be used for the formulation of remedy against the two tests bacterial under study.

5.0 Conclusion

This research work shows that both the crude (ethanol and aqueous) extracts of *Terminalia catappa*, has high antibacterial activities on the two clinical test bacteria (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella typhi*) used in this research work. The responses of the test bacteria to the crude extracts of *Terminalia catappa* leaf and the presence of very important bioactive compounds in the plant leaf has provided clue of using the leaf of *Terminalia catappa* for medicinal remedy against disease caused by the test bacteria under study.

6.0 Recommendations

There is need for further research to

- i. Extract or separate the active components presence in this leaf extracts and to test it against the bacteria under study.
- ii. Determine the toxicity of the leaf extracts using albino rats.

7.0 References

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